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Switzerland. How to Explain
Migration Policy Liberalisation to
Allow International Students
Staying after Graduation?**

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The Global Race for Talent in Switzerland. How to Explain Migration Policy Liberalisation to Allow International Students Staying after Graduation?

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Abstract

Since the 1990s, Swiss immigration policies have placed more restrictions on non-EU nationals living and working in Switzerland. However, in 2011, based on the initiative of university professor and parliamentarian Jacques Neiryneck, the Swiss Parliament approved a new law facilitating the admission and integration of non-EU nationals with a Swiss university degree. How can this policy openness in times of closure be explained? To address this question we examined the narratives crafted by Swiss parliamentarians during the parliamentary debate - both in favour of and against the draft bill. The main methods used were qualitative analysis of the minutes of parliamentary debates and in-depth interviews with key political actors. In light of our results, we propose a three-dimensional approach to explain why immigration policy liberalisation occurs: (a) the effectiveness of the *narratives* crafted by policy elites to convince parliamentarians, (b) the appropriate conditions created by the *temporal and geographical context*, and (c) the *biographical capacity* of the policy initiators to effect policy change. Emerging from this multi-dimensional approach is a unique perspective of analysis which can be used to understand policy change in migration studies.

Keywords

International student migration and mobility, immigration policy, policy change, narratives of steering, parliamentary debates, policy elite interviewing, third-countries

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1 Introduction

As the increase in globalised human mobility continues, contemporary states face a major dilemma: how to control migration flows while simultaneously attracting highly skilled workers? As a result of this tension, migration policies are becoming increasingly selective. The term 'designer immigration' (Hawthorne, 2012) refers to policies that control the selection of migrants according to how their skills may be beneficial for the knowledge economy. Using this line of reasoning, international students are often viewed by governments as 'ideal immigrants', not only because they can fill highly skilled labour gaps that many OECD countries face, but also because their assumed cultural assimilation into the host country is seen as having a positive effect in their labour market performance rather than skilled immigrants from overseas (Robertson, 2011; Chiou, 2017).

In the context of the global race for talent at the end of the 1990s, Anglo-Saxon countries put policies in place to encourage international students to remain after completion of their tertiary studies (Bedford & Spoonley, 2014; Chiou, 2017). Such policies, also known as: 'study-to-work' policies (Mosneaga, 2015), 'student switching' (Robertson, 2011), and 'two-step migration' (Hawthorne, 2012) were implemented much later in Europe, such as for example, Austria, in 2011 (Musil & Reyhani, 2012), and Germany in 2013. In 2016, since the conditions of study-to-work transition policies in the EU differed from country to country, the European Parliament approved a directive harmonising entry and residence rules in order to facilitate an easier path for students and researchers from non-EU countries¹. Students are now allowed to stay at least nine months after completing their studies in order to seek employment or start a business, and have the right to bring family members to Europe who are entitled to work during their stay (Official Journal of the European Union, 2016).

In Switzerland, international students also became a favoured source of highly skilled migrants as policies facilitating their admission and residence came into effect in 2011. Following Jacques Neiryneck's initiative in 2008, the Swiss Parliament approved amendments of the Foreign Nationals Act and of the Regulation on Admission, Residence and Employment concerning non-EU nationals that can be summarized as follows: (a) facilitated admission conditions for studying in Switzerland; (b) graduates from Swiss universities no longer required to leave Switzerland immediately after completing their tertiary education, (c) provisionally admitted to stay in Switzerland for six months after graduation to seek employment matching their qualifications, (d) not subjected to the priority rule (giving Swiss and EU citizens priority over jobs) if the prospective employment is of 'high scientific or economic interest' for Switzerland, and (e) facilitated requirements for obtaining long-term residence status (Federal Office for Migration (FOM), 2010; Vaitkeviciute, 2017). These changes represented a significant opening-up of migration policy differing from the former restrictive policies aimed at avoiding competition from non-EU nationals. How can this policy liberalisation be explained? Surprisingly, apart from legal evaluations (Vaitkeviciute, 2017), there are no social science-oriented empirical studies answering this question so far. So far, few studies have examined the relationship between immigration policies and the transnational mobility of international students, although such mobility largely depends on the legal regulations established by immigration policies (Riaño & Pigué, 2016). Some recent studies assess the policies put in place

¹ The directive entered into law the day after its publication (22 May 2016) in the European Official Journal. Member states now have two years in which to enact individual national legislation.

to increase a country's attractiveness to international students as place of tertiary education (Tham et al., 2013, Hercog & van de Laar, 2016). However, despite the increasing global trend of implementing 'study-to-work' policies that encourage the retention of international students upon completion of their studies, an empirical understanding of *how* these political debates evolve - and *why* they ultimately result in policy change (or not) - remains scant (Haugen, 2013; Hawthorne, 2012; Mosneaga, 2015). Overall, studying why migration policy changes from a restrictive to a more liberal stance still remains underexplored (Menz, 2016). This paper aims to fill a part of this research gap by achieving a deeper understanding of why policy openness in times of closure occurs.

2 The value of Switzerland as case study

Switzerland is a valuable case study for the analysis of international student' study-to-work policies for four reasons. First, at nearly 25% of the total resident population (Federal Statistical Office (FSO), 2016), it has the second-largest foreign-born population among OECD countries and depends heavily on highly skilled foreign labour. Switzerland is a small country, and has experienced a deficit of skilled workers since its industrialisation in the 19th century. Second, nearly 31% of all tertiary students (including Bachelor, Master and PhDs) enrolled in Swiss universities in 2016 had obtained their secondary degrees abroad and were foreign nationals (FSO, 2017). This represents the second-highest share of international students of all OECD countries after Luxembourg (44%) (OECD, 2016), which illustrates Switzerland's attractiveness as a place of tertiary education. The numbers of international students increased more than threefold between 1990 and 2016 (from 9'228 to 33'047), corresponding to an increase in percentage among the entire student population from 13% in 1990 to 31% in 2016 (FSO, 2017). Third, unlike Anglo-Saxon countries, where international students have become a highly profitable industry, most Swiss universities do not charge an international student fee and tuition fees are already low because of generous state funding. This suggests that studying international student mobility in Switzerland may offer an alternative understanding to the marketization perspective, currently used for English-speaking countries. Fourth, as opposed to Anglo-Saxon countries that have traditionally facilitated the permanent settlement of migrants and their naturalisation as citizens, Switzerland has been reluctant to recognise itself as a country of immigration and to grant citizenship rights to immigrants. This is characteristic of countries with a guest-worker tradition, such as Germany and Austria. Since the 1930's, Switzerland's immigration policies have largely been oriented around a protectionist narrative giving this paper an interesting platform in which to examine the shift in immigration policies to a more liberal approach.

Switzerland's immigration regime is currently characterised by 'dual foreigner's rights'. In 2002, a bilateral agreement between Switzerland and the EU came into effect that gave EU nationals the same living and working rights as the Swiss - with the exception of voting rights. Since then, legislation regarding foreigners no longer applied to EU citizens but only to individuals from countries outside the EU, usually called 'third country nationals'. In 2008, the Foreign Nationals Act came into effect, which put restrictive norms for students from third countries in place. Third-country students were obliged to submit a declaration confirming the intent of departure after the completion of their study programmes (Vaitkeviciute, 2017). Consequently, they obtained a residence permit, which only allowed them to stay in Switzerland until they had completed their

tertiary degrees. There was no direct path allowing them to seek employment and apply for a work permit after graduation. However, in exceptional cases, students considered to be of 'remarkable scientific value' were granted work permits.

In the years following the implementation of this law, academics and entrepreneurs in Switzerland expressed dissatisfaction about its seemingly arbitrary application, and the difficulties they experienced in obtaining a work permit when trying to hire students from third countries. In April 2008, Jacques Neirynek - a naturalised Belgian immigrant, parliamentarian from French-speaking Switzerland, and a professor of electrical engineering at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL) - submitted a draft bill to the Swiss Parliament to modify Article 27 of the 2005 Foreign Nationals Act. The aim was to "facilitate the admission and integration of third-country foreigners who have graduated from a Swiss university" (Curia Vista, 2017). The idea was not entirely new. Between 2000 and 2007, Neirynek - along with two other parliamentarians representing French-speaking cantons, namely Luc Barthassat and Didier Berberat - submitted three motions to Parliament to facilitate the hiring of foreign PhD students. All three parliamentarians were critical of the increasing influence of the nationalist Swiss People's Party in shaping restrictive immigration policies. Although the earlier initiatives paved the way, Neirynek's proposal was unique in that it: (a) included all foreign graduates (not just PhD students), (b) was co-signed by representatives from all political parties and linguistic regions, and (c) contained a wider range of persuasive arguments than earlier proposals.

What is the process of submitting and approving a draft bill in Switzerland? Any member of the National Council or the Council of States can submit an initiative to introduce a new law, amend an existing law, or add a new provision to the Constitution. Given the volume of legislation that Members of Parliament (MP) handle, it can be difficult to reach an informed opinion on any given issue. Therefore, before a draft bill comes before Parliament, it is discussed by parliamentary committees with the goal of agreeing on a common position which can then be supported by MPs. The committees are able to discuss legislation in greater detail, clarify specific issues, hear experts from the administration or from the interest groups concerned, and address questions to federal councillors. They also serve as a testing ground to see whether a consensus can be reached for certain proposals across party lines. Draft laws are debated up to three times by each chamber to make sure that identical decisions are reached. Although this can be a difficult process, each chamber is often ready to make compromises and adjustments. Thus, by the time a draft bill is debated in Parliament, most of the work has already been done by the committees (Swiss Confederation, 2017).

Accordingly, the political committees of the National Council and the Council of States met between 2008 and 2010 to discuss Neirynek's draft bill to facilitate the admission and integration of non-EU graduates from Swiss universities. These meetings included the preliminary examination and subsequent vote to proceed with the initiative in both chambers of Parliament (2008), followed by hearings with stakeholders (students, university and administration representatives), the debate in both chambers on a preliminary draft (2009), and the resolution of differences and final approval by the Swiss Parliament (2010). Finally, the new law was enacted on January 1st, 2011. However, the new law was not widely communicated to the broader public by the federal administration. From our interview with a canton administrator, we learned that the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne assumed the role of disseminating the information to their own students,

presumably in a bid to increase their own attractiveness with prospects of future work permits. This exemplifies an increasing trend whereby universities are becoming important actors in selecting and attracting immigrants (cf. Li & Lowe, 2016; Brunner, 2017).

3 Conceptual and methodological approach: narratives of steering, parliamentary debates, and policy elite interviews

Birkland states that public policy involves "the decisions (including both actions and non-actions) of a government or an equivalent authority" (as cited in Sabatier & Weible, 2014, p. 9), such as law, regulations, statutes, executive decisions, and government programmes. How, then, should policy change be theoretically addressed? The role of ideas in shaping policy-making has gained scholarly attention in recent decades (Bleich, 2002; Schmidt & Radaelli, 2004; Menz, 2016). Cairney (2012) states that "policy-making is not just about people exercising power to pursue their interests. It is also about the role of ideas" (p. 15–16). Menz (2016) takes this further by stating that, "policy actors instrumentally use discourse to shape the policy debate, influence the agenda and legitimise certain policy choices" (p. 627).

However, the ideational approach has not yet received much attention by migration scholars. Menz (Ibid) considers this approach as a "considerable analytical leeway in accounting for change, something other institutional approaches struggle with" (p. 627). Boswell et al. (2011), draw attention to "the potential for narratives to provide a coherent and compelling account of complex phenomena, in a way that can engender support and motivate action" (p. 4). They stress the importance of exploring how 'policy narratives' or 'narratives of steering' constructed by diverse types of actors influence immigration policy agendas. Their concept of policy narratives refers to "the factual beliefs espoused by policy-makers and others engaged in political debate about the causes and dynamics of the problems they are seeking to address, and about how policy could impact these dynamics" (Ibid.). According to them, "the success of a narrative in influencing policy agendas depends to a large extent on its consistency, coherence, plausibility and persuasiveness," and, through this, "its capacity to identify, define and constitute a policy issue or problem" (ibid.).

In this paper we focus on the argumentative power of narratives of steering to convince policy elites of the need for policy change rather than on their cognitive underpinnings. Following that conceptual framework we have formulated the following research questions:

- What narratives of steering were used by Neiryck in the Swiss Parliament to gain support for the initiative?
- What narratives of steering were used during parliamentary debates by parliamentarians and stakeholders to support or oppose Neiryck's initiative?
- Why did the narratives in favour of accepting Neiryck's initiative find broad consensus among Swiss Parliamentarians?

The research questions stated above required a qualitative approach to capturing the narratives, representations, and the political dynamics. Two methods were used: analysis of the minutes of parliamentary debates and policy elite interviewing. The minutes of the debates conducted over the

2008-2010 period by members of the National Council and the Council of States were analyzed to grasp the narratives mobilised in favour and against the bill.² The final report prepared by the Political Commission of the National Council (PCNC), which summarises the parliamentary debates and the reasons for accepting Neirynek's initiative, was also examined (PCNC, 2010). The Curia Vista database³ provided additional information on the timeline of the bill, and on similar motions previously submitted. An in-depth interview was conducted with Jacques Neirynek regarding his motivations and views on the political process. This was complemented by an interview with the head of the Department of Employment in canton Vaud inquiring as to how the policy change was communicated to the cantons and to the broader public. The minutes of parliamentary debates, as well as the interviews, were analysed using deductive coding (i.e. themes from the conceptual framework) and inductive coding (i.e. themes emerging from the analysis of the minutes of the parliamentary debate and the transcribed interviews) techniques of qualitative text analysis. All statements having the same code were grouped together in order to establish the main strands of narrative running through the text. Subsequently, we analysed each one the narrative strands against and in favour of the initiative.

Although access to political elites for the purpose of interviewing often poses many challenges, Professor and Parliamentarian Jacques Neirynek was open to being interviewed at his home. We combined biographical and semi-structured techniques for the interview, beginning with questions relating to the history of the initiative - from the moment when the problem was identified - to the acceptance of the initiative by the Swiss Parliament. This biographical approach proved successful as he was able to recap the sequence of events, providing a solid introduction to the subject. Thereafter followed the semi-structured interview questions. A total of nine topics regarding the initiative were discussed in detail, including: how the idea began; to what extent it adds to the existing law; how support was gained from other Parliamentarians; the relatively moderate opposition during parliamentary debates; canton Zurich's opposition during the consultative procedure (considering the high percentage of highly skilled workers concentrated in this canton); how to explain support for the initiative in a political system characterised by restrictive migration policies; feedback on the implementation of the law; and the future of the initiative during a severe shift to the political right.

4 Uncovering competing narratives of steering

This section examines the competing narratives of steering used by those in favour or against the Neirynek's initiative. It begins with the narratives used by Neirynek himself, the initiator of policy change, and subsequently introduces the narratives crafted by parliamentarians and stakeholders.

4.1 Narratives of steering by the initiator of policy change

What was Neirynek's motivation to initiate the policy change? During the interview, he described his personal experience as a professor and parliamentarian as motivating factors:

² In Switzerland, all parliamentary debates are recorded and transcribed in detail, constituting an invaluable source of data. The minutes of the parliamentary debates are in German and French and are made available upon request for scientific purposes.

³ Questions relating to foreigners policy are regularly asked and discussed in the Swiss Parliament. These parliamentary items have been recorded and transcribed by the Parliamentary Services since 1995 and can be consulted online via the Curia Vista database.

My motivation is my personal experience [...] When one is a parliamentarian, people who have problems contact you. And there were several foreigners who had studied here, who had graduated here, who were asked to leave within fifteen days. And, indeed, the existing Foreigners Act stated that a foreign student had to sign his commitment that he was to leave Switzerland once he obtained his diploma [describes case studies]. There was also a Tunisian who had forged a career at the EPFL, who had a doctorate, who had worked as a research assistant, etc.; he was a computer scientist and the University of Applied Science and Arts Western Switzerland was lacking computer scientists, and so he was appointed. But the Canton refused to give him a work permit, a residence permit. So that's my motivation! From that time onwards, I put this parliamentary initiative together, on the basis of a text that was written by a lawyer from Freiburg who handled such issues. (J. Neiryck, personal interview, April 15, 2016)

At the time, Neiryck was one of only two professors at the Swiss Federal Institutes of Technology who were also parliamentarians, and therefore in a key position to receive feedback from international students and companies experiencing difficulties obtaining post-graduation work permits from immigration authorities. Thus, while presenting his initiative before the political commission of the National Council, Neiryck introduced himself as a representative of the students associations, academic institutions and economic circles (Minutes of Swiss Parliamentary proceedings, 2008–2010⁴), positioning himself as a bridge between these groups. A vital personal point revealed during the interview was his arduous road to becoming a Swiss citizen, an experience which led him to conclude that immigration authorities are not able to adequately judge the “scientific value” of immigrants:

I was hired [as an EPFL professor] in Switzerland as a Belgian citizen, but it is interesting to note that I was subject to the jealousy of the people who made the decisions at the cantonal services regarding my naturalisation, and instead of taking 12 years to become naturalized it took 24 years, with two refusals. So, the problem is that some decisions important for the scientific development of the country are made by officials who have absolutely no idea of the consequences of their decisions. (Neiryck, 2016)

Now we examine the narratives of steering used by Neiryck before Parliament to legitimate changing the existing immigration law. His main argument was that “the law as it stood was a suicidal act that was contrary to the [economic] interests of the country” (Neiryck, 2016), and that Switzerland’s lack of highly skilled personnel required a shift in policy that attracted international students and encouraged them to stay. The argument he defended before Parliament was that Article 27 of the Foreigners Act essentially prevented Switzerland from producing, and more importantly retaining, experts in fields essential for the country remaining globally competitive, such as biotechnology and wealth management. Due to its declining demography, Neiryck stated that it

⁴ The legal service of the Swiss Parliament does not allow direct quotations from the minutes of the parliamentary proceedings. Therefore, information from the parliamentary minutes has been paraphrased, and no individual names from parliamentarians and stakeholders have been cited.

was imperative that Switzerland attracts and recruit talent from a pool of highly skilled personnel from beyond the borders of the European Union. By attracting young talent and training them according to Swiss norms, Switzerland would inevitably benefit economically and remain globally competitive (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

By preventing foreign graduates from staying in Switzerland after graduation, Neiryck argued that the Foreign Nationals Act was effectively wasting public funds used to train foreign students. He questioned the sustainability of this policy by stating that Switzerland pays up to one million Swiss francs for every engineer, doctor or scientist trained in Switzerland, accumulating to tens of millions of public money that is essentially lost every year when foreign graduates must leave the country. Using the EPFL's budget as an example, he cited that up to 400 million Swiss francs of the 900 million budget, was spent on foreign students who made up half of the student population. Neiryck ironically remarked that Switzerland is, however, providing its global competitors, such as the United States, with newly trained and highly qualified personnel in competitive fields such as: industry, medicine, and banking for free (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Furthermore, he lamented that Swiss administrators failed to recognise that highly skilled graduates are potential entrepreneurs who contribute to the Swiss economy through job creation. He thus elaborated that the protectionist narratives used by the administration were related to a fear in the influx of well qualified foreigners who would push Swiss nationals towards unemployment or add to the unemployment rate themselves. However, according to him, this argument failed to recognise that highly skilled graduates also created valuable jobs as evidenced by the Ecublens Science Park where two-thirds of the researchers there were foreign with over 120 start-ups in demand (Minutes of Parliamentary proceedings, 2008–2010).

He thus elaborated that the administration often puts forward an argument highlighting the risk of having an influx of foreign students who might become unemployed after eventually settling in Switzerland. For the administration, the number of jobs in Switzerland would remain the same, independent of the quality of the people involved. Any new residence permit would push a Swiss towards unemployment, especially if the foreigner is well qualified. It is thus an individual that needs to be a priori excluded. According to Neiryck, such arguments ignore the de facto situation: a highly skilled graduate creates jobs, often by launching his own start-up. As evidence he cited the Ecublens Science Park where two-thirds of the researchers there were foreign with over 120 start-ups in demand (Minutes of Parliamentary proceedings, 2008–2010).

Finally, another key point in Neiryck's argumentation is that students from non-EU countries will not return to their home countries to serve as agents of economic development - as it was formerly assumed - but will go to Switzerland's economic competitors. He argued that it is necessary to refute an argument often invoked that foreign students are trained in Switzerland with the sole purpose of returning home to contribute to its development. Such an argument is misleading since according to Neiryck nothing obliges a young scientist to return to his home country. Young researchers from developing countries do not return because it is impossible for them to exercise their profession. They often move to the United States. In addition, some students, especially the Chinese, do not come from countries in development, but from developed countries, that compete with Switzerland. Thus, Neiryck contended that Switzerland trains many managers for the global

economy, and spends public money for this purpose, but does not allow itself to recruit them and to profit from such an action (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

What kind of narrative does Neiryck construct about international students? It is clear that students represent a way to increase Switzerland's economic advantage in a globalised world. However, Neiryck's narrative of profit and economic advantage, which inevitably follows the liberalisation of immigration law, is rather narrow. Students are imagined as young, mobile, trained in fields such as engineering, biotechnology, medicine, and wealth management, and fully assimilated into Swiss culture. Moreover, he only applies the masculine form when referring to international students, a feature that is also characteristic of parliamentarian debates.

Neiryck's narrow representation of international students is reflected in the highly selective wording of the final legislation. For example, only students whose prospective jobs are of particular scientific or economic interest to Switzerland are able to obtain a work permit in Switzerland. Scientific interest is defined as "scientific work in applied research and product development, applying new technologies, or using the acquired know-how in activities of high economic interest" (FOM, 2010, p. 3). Furthermore, a "high economic interest may be present if there is a well-defined need in the labour market for the completed discipline of study, which is highly specialized and corresponds to the job description, and if filling the position directly results in creating additional jobs or new mandates for the Swiss economy" (ibid). This wording seems to fit Neiryck's view that students of economic value are exclusively engineers, bioscientists, doctors, and wealth managers.

4.2 Narratives of steering by parliamentarians and stakeholders

The parliamentary debates over Neiryck's draft bill were shaped by supporting and opposing voices. Opposition came early in the debate from representatives of federal and cantonal administrations using a protectionist logic claiming that native Swiss workers would be at risk of unemployment. This same narrative was used over subsequent hearings, however, the majority of parliamentarians agreed to proceed in favour of the draft bill. Overall, fifteen out of twenty-three cantons and four out of five political parties represented in the Federal Parliament backed the initiative. Only one party, the far-right Swiss People's Party, opposed it. Finally, when the draft bill came before the Swiss Parliament in 2010 for the final vote, it was approved by nearly 80% of parliamentarians at the National Council and 100% at the Council of States.

The minutes of the parliamentary debates show that, in terms of procedure and language, political debates in Switzerland are disciplined and respectful. Debates are preceded by an introduction of the issues by the elected president of the political commission. This is followed by opinions and questions from the participants and concluded by the commission's president who presents potential alternative actions. A vote on these alternatives follows and the session is subsequently finished. This disciplined debating culture is clearly an expression of Switzerland's democracy, largely based on consensus, which makes Switzerland a particularly interesting context for studying political discourse and policy-making processes.

Which narratives of steering did parliamentarians and stakeholders use in an attempt to direct the opinions and voting behaviour of MPs either in favour of or against the draft bill? We start with the arguments *against*. As previously mentioned, opposition was mainly expressed by representatives of the federal and cantonal administrations using a protectionist oriented narrative of steering. In their view, since it was imperative to protect native Swiss workers from foreign competition and unemployment the current law should not be changed (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Accordingly, a representative of the Federal Office for Migration (FOM) argued that the new law represented a change of paradigm in Swiss immigration policies because, so far, the principle had been that native workers should not face competition from third-country nationals. Thus, in order to protect native workers from unemployment, the existing legislation should not be changed. Another FOM representative maintained that Swiss cantons are interested in having a good economy but in times of change they do not want to have foreign students under their social budget. In the representative's view, universities never follow economic needs and fluctuations, and they want to hire students even when the economy is not doing well. Thus, it was better to keep the current law's flexible, case-by-case system, which protects Swiss cantons from having to support unemployed foreigners when the economy is in decline. The same argument was made by one of the members of the Swiss Federal Council, pleading for a demand-driven approach, claiming that allowing students to stay and seek employment would depart from well-established principles of controlling foreign access to the labour market on a case-by-case basis. Finally, a representative of the labour market authority in canton Zurich argued that the canton's economy needs foreign skilled personnel, particularly in the areas of information and communications technologies, medical technology, engineering and construction, and financing and advisory services, but the European Union provided sufficient and highly qualified personnel for those needs. The representative also expressed concern over creating a privileged group over other highly skilled migrants from non-EU countries without a Swiss degree, which complicated the administrative procedure of issuing work permits (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Which narratives of steering were used by stakeholders and parliamentarians *in favour* of the draft bill? Analysis of the minutes of parliamentary debates show three main narratives of steering: (a) Switzerland's image suffers under the current law, (b) Switzerland needs to be competitive in a globalised economy and take advantage of global opportunities, and (c) foreign students trained in Switzerland have the advantage of already being culturally assimilated.

We start with the arguments expressed by stakeholders during the hearings. A representative of the Network for the Dialogue between Science and Politics argued that the message was quickly passed among foreign students that Switzerland is very restrictive, which damages the country's image. For the students the law seemed so strict and unavoidable that many would assess the situation as hopeless and won't even apply to stay. Thus, instead of going to the Federal Institutes of Technology in Zurich or Lausanne, students will go to Berkeley (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Moving on to the arguments of debating parliamentarians, a member of parliament argued that students who do not stay in Switzerland will inevitably become competitors. The argument was presented that students from outside the European Union now come from countries that are Switzerland's commercial competitors, particularly the BRIC countries (Brazil, Russia, India,

China). When these students return to their countries of origin they will be hired by competitor firms and thus Switzerland has given these firms the weapons to fight the country (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

The above argument illustrates a shift in views about students from non-European countries that is present in much of the debate. Formerly, these students were seen as agents of development for their native countries upon their return. However, this is now doubted and they are now viewed as potential competitors in the global economy. The concern of ‘brain drain’, a term prominently used in public discourses in the 1980s, is no longer present as students are primarily viewed as agents of innovation for Switzerland’s economy. Until the 1980s, Swiss development policies viewed foreign students as agents of innovation for so-called “countries in development”. Swiss universities were thus expected to play a capacity-building role.

Another parliamentarian argued further that Asian students trained in Switzerland could be used as key agents for Swiss companies in order to take advantage of global economic opportunities. As an example, the argument was presented that in the canton of Vaud, a large Swiss informatics company had a subsidiary in Vietnam. It would be more interesting for the company to employ Asian students (rather than Europeans), especially Vietnamese, in order to establish a good relationship with the subsidiary of Vietnam (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Finally, the idea of capitalising on the acquired cultural assimilation of foreign graduates, was presented by another parliamentarian who posed the question if it is not better to hire a student from outside the European Union, who has been trained in Swiss schools, rather than a European student trained in France, Germany, or Spain (Minutes of proceedings, 2008–2010).

Overall, the protectionist approach defended by Swiss administrators did not resonate with parliamentarians. As stated in the Report of the Political Commission of the National Council (PCNC, 2010), the commission supported the liberalisation of the Foreigners Act for the following reasons: first, it noted the considerable differences in how the individual cantons implemented the Foreigners Act, often to the disadvantage of international students and to the detriment of Switzerland’s position as a powerful educational and economic centre. Second, the former law made it difficult, and sometimes impossible, for third-country students - who represent, according to them, well over 30% of all foreign students in Switzerland - to remain in Switzerland after completing their tertiary education. Consequently, the country failed to keep highly skilled specialists who, instead of taking employment in Switzerland or creating their own business, went elsewhere. Third, educational costs in Switzerland are heavily subsidised by the federal and cantonal governments. Instead of profiting from this investment, Switzerland’s competing economies are the beneficiaries. Subsequently, the Foreigners Act was changed in 2011 to facilitate the admission and labour market integration of third-country nationals with a Swiss university degree.

5 Understanding policy openness in times of closure

How can this policy-shift toward openness in times of restrictive immigration policies be explained? We propose three complementary explanations: the role of narratives of steering, the role of the spatio-temporal context, and the role of the personal history of the policy initiator.

5.1 The role of narratives of steering

Asked in the interview why he believes his initiative succeeded, Neiryneck responds that "good sense prevailed." His economic narrative states that in the global competition for highly skilled workers, Switzerland ultimately loses out on this valuable pool of human resources - which it has paid to educate - to competing economies. The narrative of economic benefit appealed to parliamentarians from different political orientations. Also, his argument fulfils Boswell et al.'s (2011) theory that for narratives to succeed in influencing policy agendas they need to be plausible, compelling, and resonate with perceived interests. Moreover, Neiryneck uses real case studies and dramatic statistics on public spending to persuasively argue that the former law not only affects third-country students, but ultimately Switzerland's global position as an educational and economic centre. He describes this particular immigrant group as unproblematic, highly specialized, trained according to Swiss cultural norms, and being in high demand in the labour market. By representing them as young, innovative entrepreneurs, he plausibly highlights their potential contributions to Switzerland's global competitiveness. In conclusion, Neiryneck's narratives of steering are more persuasive than the protectionist narrative used by representatives of the administration.

In examining the recent liberalisation of labour migration schemes in Europe, Menz (2016, p. 628) also observes how policy elites successfully use the global competitiveness narrative by claiming that a "so-called 'global battle for brains' is underway, in which countries with restrictive migration policies lose out in gaining access to an otherwise readily available global talent pool". The success of such narrative can also be interpreted in Cerny's sense that contemporary states have become 'competition states' whereby political actors try to capture global economic potentials (1990, p. 225).

However, the Swiss case is unique in that the main narrative of steering is not simply about global economic competitiveness but also about a return on public funds investments. As previously stated, the Swiss state heavily subsidises the university costs of international students providing Neiryneck with a compelling argument that Switzerland loses the brains it has trained to its international competitors. Moreover, in a federalist country where each canton is governed semi-autonomously, the narrative concerning disparities of practice within these regions finds particular resonance among Swiss MPs in enacting policy change.

5.2 The role of the geographical and temporal context

We propose that the effectiveness of narratives of steering to effect policy change largely depends on how favourable the *geographical and temporal context* is. Temporally speaking, global and local events had a positive effect on policy change, for example: the globally circulating narratives during the late 1990s about the need to attract international talent to be globally competitive; the regulations implemented by the European Union in 2009 to facilitate the post-graduation retention of third-country students; and the motions that Neiryneck and other MPs had previously submitted to liberalise immigration policy effecting international students. Moreover, the debate on depleting poor countries of their best and brightest seemed to be outdated in the Swiss context, which works

in favour of the argument to retain students. Also, in 2008, at the time the initiative was introduced, the steady increase in the numbers of EU migrants resulting from the 2002 Agreement on the Free Movement of Persons (AFMP) with the EU was not yet visible to the Swiss public.

Looking at the geographical context, Switzerland is a small country - both in size and population. The elected MPs only serve on a part-time basis, as many work as entrepreneurs, academics, and trade unionists, for example. This particular context allows initiators of policy change, such as Neiryck, to be in close contact with key stakeholders, and to know, first hand, the interests of the groups they represent. Moreover, Switzerland's political system based on transparency, stakeholder participation, disciplined debate, and political consensus makes it a uniquely favourable context for a powerful narrative of steering to succeed.

5.3 The role of biographical capacity

The concept of *biographical capacity*, which we define as the biographical experiences equipping a person with the knowledge and personal contacts to occupy a legitimate position to push for change, further explains why policy change can occur. Occupying both roles of university professor and Member of Parliament, Neiryck was in daily contact with international students sharing their negative experiences in obtaining a work permit. This enriched his understanding of the issues and motivated him to represent their interests in the Swiss Parliament. Furthermore, as a former immigrant, he was in a good position to understand the arbitrary decision-making by immigration authorities. Moreover, he had spent over twenty years in Parliament, which gave him an in-depth knowledge of the system, along with personal contacts with other MPs. This helped to further facilitate his in-house political support of the initiative. Embodying the double role of academic and experienced MP gave him a solid platform in which to argue before Swiss parliamentarians. Finally, through his life and work experiences in Europe, Africa, and the United States, he developed the conviction that research knows no national borders and promoted the idea of 'research without passport', as stated in the interview. Thus, as an EPFL professor, parliamentarian, former immigrant, and world citizen, Jacques Neiryck had specific motivations and legitimate expertise with which to successfully defend his initiative in Parliament. Biographical capacity is an invaluable tool when analysing and seeking to understand policy change from the perspective of a policy maker's actions.

6 Conclusion

Using the concept of narratives of steering, this paper examined the recent policy shift in Switzerland to facilitate the international mobility and labour market integration of non-EU graduates of Swiss universities, despite prevailing restrictive policies towards non-EU immigrants. Carrying out qualitative analysis of the minutes of the parliamentary debates leading up to the approval of the new policy and in-depth interviews with key political actors, has proven invaluable in uncovering the narratives constructed by policy elites to legitimate policy change. This paper demonstrates that 'designer migrants' (Hawthorne, 2012) are allowed special streams of entry and labour market integration - even during periods of general closure in migration management - because they are viewed by policy elites as valuable assets that help increase Switzerland's economic competitiveness. Indeed, in times of strict migration management, policy makers employ a

utilitarian discourse to justify their selectiveness towards migrants who supposedly contribute most to economic growth (Piguët, 2006; de Haas et al., 2016).

However, despite striking similarities with the competitiveness discourse used by policy makers in Europe (Menz, 2016) and New Zealand and Australia (Bedford & Spoonley, 2014), the narrative used by Neiryneck - highlighting the forced departure of international students upon completion resulting in a loss of millions of francs for the country - appears to be a uniquely Swiss one. This is illustrated by the fact that international students are essentially educated for free by the Swiss state. By arguing that Switzerland's loss of public investment is essentially a gain for other global competitors, Neiryneck uses a powerful economic narrative to convince MPs of the need for policy liberalisation.

This study demonstrates that *narratives of steering* by policy elites are significant in influencing policy change in international student migration. We pose the question, however, are narratives of steering, *per se*, are sufficient enough to effect policy change, independent of the geographical and temporal context and the specific actors pushing for policy change? We suggest that by viewing narratives of steering as not being performed in a vacuum but in specific *temporal and geographical contexts* (comprising temporality and the location, size, political system and policy-making history of a country or a region), one can see favourable or unfavourable conditions for such narratives to succeed. Further, we suggest using a perspective that views policy change as not simply pushed forward by abstract actors, but that specific individuals having the *biographical capacity* to effect policy change are in a particularly favourable position to succeed. In proposing this concept, we understand biographical capacity to be the life experiences equipping a person with the knowledge and personal contacts to occupy a legitimate position to push for change.

Although the new law facilitating the migration and retention of international students from third-countries represents an important opening-up in an otherwise closed political system, it is, however, highly selective. Only individuals with a Swiss degree, in a profession with proven shortages in the labour market, or the ability to develop new products and technologies for a globally competitive market, stand to profit from this change. Similarly, this conclusion echoes de Haas et al.'s (2016) that migration policies increasingly aim to affect the selection of immigrants rather than volume. The growing emphasis on specific criteria demonstrates that “the real aim of most migration policies seems to be to increase the ability of states to control *who* is allowed to immigrate” (Ibid p. 30). Our case study clearly demonstrates this assertion.

Some questions remain open for future research. First, to what extent is the window of opportunity opened by the new law merely a symbolic one? Second, considering the legislative autonomy the cantons enjoy, to what extent will the difference in the implementation of the law persist? Third, as third-country migrants are increasingly required to fit into narrow profiles, what will the implications of such selective policies be in terms of stratification of residential and labour rights? Fourth, in a country where immigration policies have created tension between the protectionist interests of nationalist parties and the needs of a knowledge-oriented economy since the 1930s, what is the future of international student mobility policies? Will the current liberalisation continue? Will it be reversed? These questions need to be empirically addressed.

In summary, our study contributes to the literature on policy change in international student mobility by proposing an explanatory model that combines three dimensions: (a) effective *narratives of steering* crafted by policy elites to influence policy change, (b) a *temporal and geographical context* creating favourable conditions for those narratives to succeed, and (c) policy elites having the *biographical capacity* to influence policy agendas. This theoretical model will be useful for studies of migration policy change in general. This research is also of interest for scholars seeking to explain spatial variations across countries and regions on why migration policy changes - from a restrictive stance to a more liberal one or vice versa.

References

- Bedford, R. & Spoonley, P. (2014). Competing for Talent: Diffusion of an Innovation in New Zealand's Immigration Policy. *International Migration Review*, 48 (3), 891–911.
- Bleich, E. (2002). Integrating ideas into policy-making analysis: Frames and race policies in Britain and France. *Comparative Political Studies*, 35 (9), 1054–1076.
- Boswell, C., Geddes, A. & Scholten, P. (2011). The role of narratives in migration policy-making: A research framework. *British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 13 (1), 1–11.
- Brunner, L.R (2017). Higher educational institutions as emerging immigrant selection actors: a history of British Columbia's retention of international graduates, 2001–2016. *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 1 (1), 22-41.
- Cairney, P. (2012). *Understanding public policy: Theories and issues*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cerny, G.P. (1990). *The changing architecture of politics: Structure, agency and the future of the state*. London: Sage.
- Chiou, B. (2017). Two-step migration: A comparison of Australia's and New Zealand's policy development between 1998 and 2010. *Asian Pacific Migration Journal*, 26 (1), 84-107.
- Curia Vista (2017). *Database of parliamentary proceedings*. The Swiss Parliament, Federal Assembly. Retrieved from <https://www.parlament.ch/en/ratsbetrieb/curia-vista>.
- de Haas, H., Natter, K. & Vezzoli, S. (2016). Growing restrictiveness or changing selection? The nature and evolution of migration policies. *International Migration Review*, 1–44.
- Federal Office for Migration (2010). *Information. Erleichterte Zulassung und Integration von drittstaatsangehörigen Ausländerinnen und Ausländern mit Schweizer Hochschulabschluss / Umsetzung der Parlamentarischen Initiative Neiryneck (08.407)*. Nr. 2010-12-20/49.
- Federal Statistical Office (2016). *Switzerland's population 2015*. Neuchâtel: FSO.
- Federal Statistical Office (2017). *Students enrolled at Swiss tertiary institutions according to the place of their secondary education, level of study and year of enrolment (In German)*. <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/dienstleistungen/forschung/stat-tab-online-datenrecherche.html> [accessed: 23.08.2017].
- Haugen, H. Ø. (2013). China's recruitment of African university students: Policy efficacy and unintended outcomes. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 11 (3), 315–334.
- Hawthorne, L. (2012). Designer immigrants? International students and two-step migration. In D.K. Deardorff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of International Higher Education* (417-435). Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- Hercog, M. & van de Laar, M. (2016). Europe as unlikely immigrant destination: location choice for internationally mobile students in India. *European Journal of Higher Education* 6 (4), 356-371.
- Li, Z. & Lowe, J. (2016). Mobile student to mobile worker: the role of universities in the 'war for talent'. *British Journal of Sociology of Education* 37 (1), 11-29.
- Menz, G. (2016). Framing competitiveness: The advocacy of migration as an essential human resources strategy in Europe. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42 (4), 625–642.

Minutes of Swiss Parliamentary Proceedings on the Jacques Neiryneck draft bill: Commissions of the National Council and the Council of States. (2008, August 22–2010, June 8). Bern: Legal Department of Parliament Services, Switzerland.

Mosneaga, A. (2015). Managing international student migration: The practices of institutional actors in Denmark. *International Migration*, 53 (1), 14–28.

Musil, E. & Reyhani, A. (2012). *Zuwanderung Internationaler Studierender aus Drittstaaten nach Österreich*. Studie des Nationalen Kontaktpunkts Österreich im Europäischen Migrationsnetzwerk. Internationale Organisation für Migration, Länderbüro Wien.

Neiryneck, J. (2016, April 15). Personal interview with the first author. Bern, Switzerland. Audio recording / unpublished transcript (unpaginated).

Official Journal of the European Union, (2016). Directive (EU) 2016/801 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of research, studies, training, voluntary service, pupil exchange schemes or educational projects and au pairing, 2016 O.J. L 132/21.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2016). *Education at a Glance 2016: OECD Indicators*. Paris: OECD.

Piguet, E. (2006). Economy versus the people ? Swiss immigration policy between economic demand, xenophobia and international constraint. In *Dialogues on Migration Policy* edited by Marco Giugni and Florence Passy, 67-89. Oxford: Lexington Books.

Political Commission of the National Council (PCNC). (2010). Parliamentary initiative facilitating the admission and integration of foreigners with a Swiss university degree (in German). Report of the Political Commission of the National Council (PCNC). *Bundesblatt* Nr. 5: BBI 2010427.

Riaño, Y. & Piguet, E. (2016). International student migration. In Barney Warf (Ed.), *Oxford Bibliographies in Geography*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Robertson, S. (2011). Student switchers and the regulation of residency: The interface of the individual and Australia's immigration regime. *Population, Space and Place*, 17 (1), 103–115.

Sabatier, P.A. & Weible, C.M. (Eds.) (2014). *Theories of the policy process*. Philadelphia: Westview Press.

Schmidt, V.A. & Radaelli, C. (2004). Policy change and discourse in Europe: Conceptual and methodological issues. *West European Politics*, 27 (2), 183–210.

Swiss Confederation. (2017). *The Swiss Parliament*. Retrieved from <https://www.admin.ch/gov/en/start/federal-council/political-system-of-switzerland/swiss-parliament.html>.

Tham, S.Y., Mahmud, N.K. & Alavi, R. (2013). Assessing policies for attracting international students: case of Malaysia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 33 (1), 112-126.

Vaitkeviciute, A. (2017). Migration and mobility of third-country researchers and students in the European Union and Switzerland. In: *Jusletter*, February 13 2017.